

Small Livestock Production : A Potential Agri-Business in Rural India

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Abstract

The commercial goat and sheep farming is coming up fast in India. India has 148.9 million goat, 109.9 million buffaloes and 74.3 million sheep population. It plays an important role on the development of rural socio-economy particularly in dry land and denuded hilly tracts. There are great opportunities for rural employment of resource-less poor population. The meat production, which jibes well with dairying, is placed at No. 8 position in the world. India produces about 4.9 million tonnes of meat annually valued as \$4,600 million, and has grown @ 4.5% during the last two decades. However, during the last five years, this segment has been growing very fast at the rate of 27% annually and has a good future given the present attention by the government and private entrepreneurs. The need of the day is to increase carcass weight and reproductive efficiency with a strategy to produce more quality meat/animal through scientific approach. Therefore, it is necessary to support the small ruminant production sector in the country to meet the gap of quality protein supply in the country and to enhance the export potential of organic meat of Indian origin.

Key words: Agri-Business, India, Small Livestock, Production.

Introduction

Goat and sheep rearing have been proved to be the most remunerative enterprise amongst various livestock activities. For small households, surviving on subsistence farming, small ruminant act as a cushion and some kind of financial security. They constitute an important disposable asset to tide over periods of financial stress and retain a part of the asset for continuing the enterprise. Goat is nicely termed as "poor man's cow" by our father of the nation Mahatma Gandhi. It plays an important role on the development of rural socio-economy particularly in dry land and denuded hilly tracts. There are great opportunities for rural employment of resource-less poor population.

India has 148.9 million goat, 109.9 million buffaloes and 74.3 million sheep population (livestock census Mo FAHD DAHD, GoI 2019). It is significant to note that a large proportion of the rural population below the poverty line is therefore, concentrated around the waste lands.

The commercial goat and sheep farming is coming up fast in India. The balance scientific feeding schedule to maximise the return from the goat enterprise under intensive feeding system has some advantages over extensive or semi-intensive system of management, due to scarcity of grazing land. The feed requirement of the goats is to be rationalized to reduce the expenditure on cut and carry method or purchase of forage. Therefore, poor soil or unused land may be utilized for silvi-pasture development to increase the quality biomass yield per unit of land; thereby, goat and sheep production can be increased through silvi-pasture development. At the same time the soil fertility can be improved through this practice.

The meat industry is the collective of diverse businesses that together supply much of the food energy consumed by the world population. Even though food processing is among the largest industries, India ranks fifth in terms of production, consumption, export and expected growth. Food processing industry is widely recognized as a 'sunrise industry' having huge potential for uplifting agricultural economy,

creation of large scale processed food manufacturing and food chain facilities, and the resultant generation of employment and export earnings. India has enormous growth potential from its current status of being the world's second largest food producer to be the world's number one producer.

Meat processing industry also is of enormous significance for India's development because of the vital linkages and synergies that it promotes. Meat processing covers a spectrum of products from sub-sector comprising animal husbandry and poultry farms, and bulk frozen meat, packaged meat, ready-to-eat processed meat products. Essentially, the meat industry involves the commercial movement of food from farm to fork. While India has an abundant supply of meat, the meat processing industry is still nascent.

There is increasing demand for livestock produced by organic or ecological farming methods. The food products produced by the use of pesticides, antibiotics, and chemical additives etc. are considered harmful to the health of human population. Therefore, the products obtained from the small ruminants being maintained on natural feed resources have high importance because these are not harmful to the health of consumers.

Demand and Supply of Feeds for Small Ruminant Production

Cataloguing feed resources for goats in different parts of India is a very important part for their sustainability and higher productivity. In India, there exists a marked imbalance between total ruminant livestock units and available permanent pastures. Attempts should be made to explore better utilization of goat friendly feed resources. Conventional ingredients like grains and oilseed cakes are used mainly for milk production purposes from cows and buffaloes. Therefore, small ruminants are given least priority for conventional ingredients to be incorporated in their ration. Hence, alternate feed resources including enriched straws/hay may be used for intensive and semi-intensive goat rearing systems. Use of by-products particularly pulses will reduce the cost of feed and the competition between large ruminants and small ruminants.

Growth Potential of Meat Sector

Though the Indian meat production has been growing at a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 5% during the last one decade, there is a considerable concern to a certain extent about production, which remains static or flow at the present growth rate of 2% annually. Meat exports are likely to increase at an annual growth rate of about 10%. While in the previous year 2005-06, the exports touched a spectacular 48%. The export of buffalo meat has been growing at a CAGR of about 8%. The country produces an estimated 1.5 million tonnes of buffalo meat annually. Of this, about 24% is exported. Meat is primarily exported to the Philippines, Malaysia, West Asian countries like the UAE, Saudi Arabia, Qatar, Oman etc. African and CIS countries.

Export potential of meat and meat products (in US \$ million)

year	World	%_Change_IN_World	India	%_Change_IN_INDIA	India's share(%)
1970	3584	NA	4	NA	0.1
1975	7378	105.86	9	125	0.1
1980	17832	141.69	67	644.44	0.4
1985	15755	-11.65	61	-8.96	0.4
1990	34118	116.55	77	26.23	0.2
2000	44690	30.99	324	320.78	0.7
2010	112000	150.62	1821	462.04	1.6
2014	151800	35.54	5079	178.91	3.3
2015	132000	-13.04	4347	-14.41	3.3
2019	156200	18.33	3453	-20.57	2.2
2020	155058	-0.73	3109	-9.96	2.0

Sources: Economic Survey 2022-23 Govt. of India

As we can clearly see, There are Increasing trends in both of the diagrams.

It is clear from the presented data that there has been an unprecedented change in meat export between 2010 and thereafter, but after 2015 there has been a decline in meat export. It is absolutely necessary to consider the reasons for this. Livestock sector contributes 4.11% GDP and 25.6 % of total Agriculture GDP. It is evident that there is enough scope to increase the export potential of meat in India. With the overwhelming success of the Green and White Revolution, India is now fervently for the Pink Revolution that will ensure diversification and large investments in meat-food-processing.

The share of bovine meat in the total meat production in India is about 60% as against small ruminants (15%), pigs (10%) and poultry (12%). To produce the above quantities, the extraction rates in cattle are about 6%, buffaloes 11%, sheep 33%, goat 38% and pigs 84%.

India exports, both frozen and fresh chilled meat to more than 54 countries in the world. For the year 2001-2002 export was 243,560 MT. The major export was of deboned and deglanded buffalo meat, which accounts for 98% of the total meat exports. The rest of the meat exported is from sheep, goat and poultry. Meat is produced from animals procured from disease free zones and processed in the state of the art processing plants following world class sanitary and phytosanitary measures and certified with Hazard Analysis Critical Control Point (HACCP) and ISO-9002. There is, however, very little processing of meat (1%) for ready to eat meat products.

There are around 10 fully integrated eco-friendly processing plants in the country with processing capacity of producing 50,000 to 120,000 tonnes of meat per annum. Six more fully integrated meat plants are already in the process of construction. Meat industry has shown a tremendous change in the last one decade with the establishment of the eco-friendly fully integrated processing plants and in the next ten years, there will also be great change with the establishment of the feedlots as a backward

integration to the processing plants. With the Government of India taking up Foot and Mouth Disease (FMD) control programme in three zones in the country (North, Central and South) consisting of 56 districts, it is assumed that India is poised with a major breakthrough in the meat and dairy product exports in the international markets. If India had the “Green Revolution”, the “White Revolution”, and the “Blue Revolution”, can the “Pink Revolution” be far behind?

About five million households in the country are engaged in the rearing of small ruminants (sheep, goats and rabbits) and other allied activities. The production of wool was 33.0 million kg during 2021-22. Compared to previous year, wool production is continuously decreasing. Despite this, India ranks 9th in world wool production.

A Centrally Sponsored Scheme “Assistant to States for modernisation/ improvement of abattoirs and establishment of carcass utilisation centres and primary hide flaying units” was implemented. The objectives of the scheme were to provide wholesome and hygienic meat, gainful utilisation of animal by-products, prevention of environmental pollution and cruelty to animals. Under the scheme, financial assistance of Rs. 14.15 crore was provided for incomplete projects to States of Arunachal Pradesh, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Uttar Pradesh, Nagaland, Kerala, Tripura and Union Territory of Chandigarh during 2004-05. The scheme has now been discontinued as per Zero Based Budgeting (ZBB) decision.

Conservation of Threatened Breeds

Population of some of the pure-breed small ruminants, equines, pigs and pack animals has come down considerably and such breeds have come to the category of threatened breeds in the country. The farms or the farmers unit in their respective breeding tract are to be established with cent per cent Central assistance for breeds of these animals wherein their population is less than 10,000 with active participation of State Governments and NGOs, etc. There are some goat and sheep breeds in India which are considered threatened at present. These breeds need to be protected through Government assistance in breeding, feeding and management practices.

A new Centrally Sponsored Scheme for conservation of such threatened breeds has been started during Tenth Five-Year plan with a budget outlay of Rs 1500 lakh. During 2005-06, an amount of Rs. 406.92 lakh has been released for conservation of Terrasa Goat (Rs 20.00 lakh) in Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Bhutia Pony (Rs 44.39 lakh) in Arunachal Pradesh, Yak (Rs 13.00 lakh) in Himachal Pradesh, Zanskari Horse (Rs 29.96 lakh) and Double Humped Camel (Rs 29.85) in Jammu & Kashmir, Madgyal Sheep (Rs 64.50 lakh) in Maharashtra, Jamunapari Goat (Rs 59.87 lakh) in Uttar Pradesh, Gray Sindhi Horse (Rs 19.70 lakh) in Punjab, and Ghoongro pig (Rs 31.15 lakh) Bonpala Sheep (Rs 30.00 lakh) and Garole Sheep (Rs 32.25 lakh) & Black Bengal Goat (Rs 32.25 lakh) in West Bengal. There is a budget provision of Rs 400 lakh under the scheme during 2006-07.

Government Policies

The sustainability of the livestock production system in the country is handicapped due to perpetual shortage of feed and fodder. Even though the Indian livestock industry by and large is dependent on the agricultural residues or waste material and naturally available green fodder. Alternative remunerativeness of agro-residues has further reduced their availability for livestock. This is compounded by the fact that common property/grazing facilities are fast depleting. Sometimes, unprecedented draught conditions in the larger part of the country has brought the problem to sharp focus. Even though the various aspects of the calamity relief are being monitored and remedial measures coordinated under National Disaster Management (NDM) division under Department of Agriculture and Cooperation, it is required to address the problem of feed and fodder shortage by undertaking long term measures supported by legislative back up so that fodder cultivation as an integral part of the land use plan of the state is ensured. A mission mode project on Fodder may be thought of for drought proofing and long-term solutions.

- Feed is a major input for livestock production. Compounded balanced feed is one way of better nutrient management. The need to have better quality control and standards for feeds cannot be over emphasized. Regulation of quality of feed stuffs is the need of the hour.

- Importance of generating reliable disease information, based on verifiable database is increasing. This would call for tapping all the potential existing in the state, universities and other sister organizations in line with establishment of four Regional Laboratories and Central Laboratory using the facilities of the state and ICAR institutions. The current animal quarantine and risk analysis systems would need strengthening in terms of infrastructure and competence. Hence there is need to focus on human resource development in this regard.
- The programmes pursued by the Department under various schemes for prevention and control of various diseases has provided excellent results. No new exotic diseases have been reported from the country. The National Rinderpest Eradication Programme has achieved another milestone by obtaining the zonal "Substantive Freedom Status" from OIE for three out of the four zones of the country. New Vaccines for the control of "Pesti petit des ruminant" or "PPR" (a disease of small ruminant similar to Rinderpest but caused by different virus) has been cleared for commercial production, development of a diagnostic kit for sero-surveillance of Rinderpest has been developed and approved by OIE. A Large programme to develop "Disease Free Zone" with particular reference to Foot and Mouth Disease is also being contemplated.
- The regulatory mechanism for the import and export of Livestock and Livestock Products has been given appropriate legal support by undertaking the amendment of Livestock Importation Act. However, the absence of a uniform legislation for the control of movement of livestock across the country is a handicap for effective control of diseases. The Infectious and Contagious Diseases Act, which is in final stages of approval, would further strengthen the regulatory mechanism and disease control efforts. It will be essential to ensure wholehearted support of the state machinery to these regulatory measures.
- Higher growth in livestock sector would call for better quality inputs and services required for livestock production. And quality of goods and services can only be ensured through standardization and quality measures. This will apply for all items but for animal feed, vaccines and biological, semen and embryos, these would be essential.
- The negotiations have resulted in four main portions of the Agreement; the Agreement on Agriculture itself; the concessions and commitments Members are to undertake on market access, domestic support and export subsidies; the Agreement on Sanitary and Phytosanitary Measures; and the Ministerial Decision concerning Least-Developed and Net Food-Importing Developing countries.
- Overall, the results of the negotiations provide a framework for the long-term reform of agricultural trade and domestic policies over the years to come. It makes a decisive move towards the objective of increased market orientation in agricultural trade. The rules governing agricultural trade are strengthened which will lead to improved predictability and stability for importing and exporting countries alike.
- The agricultural package provides for commitments in the area of market access, domestic support and export competition. The text of the Agricultural Agreement is mirrored in the GATT Schedules of legal commitments relating to individual countries.
- In the area of market access, non-tariff border measures are replaced by tariffs that provide substantially the same level of protection. Tariffs resulting from this "tariffication" process, as well as other tariffs on agricultural products, are to be reduced by an average 36 per cent in the case of developed countries and 24 per cent in the case of developing countries, with minimum reductions for each tariff line being required. Reductions are to be undertaken over six years in the case of developed countries and over ten years in the case of developing countries.

Conclusion

Two-third of world's poor live in Asia below defined poverty lines and more than 65% of them are poor livestock keepers deriving their economic sustenance from small ruminant rearing. Small and marginal farmers or land less labourers with negligible land holding for conventional agriculture rely

on livestock, particularly small ruminant rearing for their sustenance. Sheep and goat rearing is less capital intensive operated by employing surplus family labour or women and children on community rangeland under extensive range management. Agro-climatically large part of the country is semiarid and arid where conventional agriculture is always a gamble due to erratic rain and frequent failure of monsoon; hence, livestock particularly small ruminant play pivotal role in agrarian economy. Sheep were earlier reared for wool as the major produce while with paradigm shift in agriculture meat has replaced wool.

In spite of big potential of the large livestock population, meat industry in India has not taken its due share although India has acquired number one position in the world contributing 13% of the world milk production. The meat production, which jibes well with dairying, is placed at No. 8 position in the world. India produces about 4.9 million tonnes of meat annually valued as \$4,600 million, and has grown @ 4.5% during the last two decades. However, during the last five years, this segment has been growing very fast at the rate of 27% annually and has a good future given the present attention by the government and private entrepreneurs.

More than 70% Indian consumers are non-vegetarian by choice with preference for sheep and goat meat. With rapid urbanization and improvement in economic status, the demand for meat is likely to increase further than the present level of 6 kg/person/year. Moreover, the demand for meat in southern states, J & K and export market is increasing rapidly requiring development of technology to meet the challenge. The advantage of large population size, comparatively leaner meat yield suited for elite caloric conscious consumers, organic production, increasing demand of domestic market and export avenues due render the venture promising for investment by entrepreneurs. Various system of small ruminant production is practiced world over while the existing system of extensive range management and developed system of grazing with supplementation and intensive feeding has relevance in Indian context, which was mainly due to shrinking of agriculture land in the country. Moreover, under extensive range management the small ruminants are practically reared on organic production system hence their produce can fetch premium price in high-end domestic and international markets. The need of the day is to increase carcass weight and reproductive efficiency with a strategy to produce more quality meat/animal through scientific approach. Therefore, it is necessary to support the small ruminant production sector in the country to meet the gap of quality protein supply in the country and to enhance the export potential of organic meat of Indian origin.

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